

**ANALYTICAL STUDY: EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING AND
DEVELOPMENT OF EMPLOYEE IN APPIN TECHNOLOGY,
COIMBATORE**

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Abstract:

Employees are the most valuable asset of an organization, so to enhance their performance it is necessary to pay attention to their learning. Training and development programs help organizations to build a skilled and competent workforce in order to maintain a high level of competency and to survive in a dynamic business environment. This study was conducted with the aim to investigate the effectiveness of training and development on employee performance at App in Technology, Coimbatore. The research employed descriptive analysis. Primary data was collected through distributing questionnaires to 100 employees, who were selected through the random sampling technique. Findings reveal that overall training and development has a significant impact on employee's performance. It helps the organization in reducing employee turnover, increasing the productivity of employees, and contributing to higher financial returns for the organization. The study suggests that there is a need for improvisation in identifying the area where training needs have actually generated and salary structure should be revised at a regular interval of time.

Key Words: Training, Development, Employee Performance, Organization

Introduction:

Training and development are a part of an organization's subsystem that focuses on improving individual and group of employees. Training is the method of improving an employee's skill, knowledge, and abilities in order for them to perform a specific job. Employee development refers to their overall development. It is process by which managers and executives develop experience and competency in their current job, as well as the ability to perform future tasks.

Training:

Training is a broad phase that covers a variety of industries, technical information, and other aspects related to the internal processes that a business relies on to function. The Training is a process of increasing the knowledge and skills of an employee for doing the particular job. It seeks to improve the job performance and work behavior of those trained.

Development:

Development is a process of improving employees existing competencies and skills and developing newer ones to support the organizational goals. With help from their employer, employees can take time to learn how to use new technologies and techniques, develop their knowledge of an industry or subject matter, and grow their competencies across different areas.

Employee Training and Development:

Any action that includes helping employees enhance their knowledge and skills or improve existing or acquire new skills is known as employee training and development. Development is gaining new information, abilities, or perspectives that equip employees with new directions and responsibilities. Training is just one form of employee learning; others include self-learning, informal learning, coaching, mentoring, and more. Employee training and development means investing energy, time, and resources that eventually improve the company's personnel. While employee training focuses on helping the employee do the current job better. It focuses on helping the employee solve the problems that they are facing and helps them develop the skills to solve them. It acts as an upgrade in the current job role.

Breaking Down Employee 'Training' and 'Development':

Employee training and development may sound similar but both have different meanings and roles. An employee training refers to a short-term activity that focuses on the specific role of the employee. It focuses on the immediate need or requirement of the role. Employee development has open-ended goals and doesn't focus on one job but the entirety of an individual. While employee training focuses on helping the employee do the current job better, development helps groom employees for newer possibilities and roles.

Types of Employee Training and Development:

Technical Training:

You might have employees who are perfect in whatever job roles they have, be it accounting, content writing, SEO, or more. But you must have heard that no knowledge goes unused, and there is always room for improvement and learning. Tech is constantly upgrading and changing, and as a company, you must invest in your employees to acquire relevant skills and boost their knowledge.

Customer Service Training:

Employees who work in customer service are coached to enhance customer support and happiness. A solid customer service training program includes improving interpersonal communication, product knowledge, dispute resolution, crisis management, and other skills.

Leadership Development:

Leadership development training is vital to any organization's growth and success. It can help develop the skills and competencies of individuals, teams, and the organization. In addition, leadership development training can be tailored to address specific needs, such as developing a team-oriented culture, growing communication skills, fostering creativity and innovation, or helping to create a more diverse and inclusive workplace.

Safety Training:

Safety training is not only necessary in an organization but also for a person's personal use. Make sure employees understand the safety procedures and protocols relevant to their job. Teach employees how to use safety equipment properly. Employees should know who is responsible for safety at the workplace and who to turn to during safety emergencies and provide regular safety reminders. The training encompasses customer safety, employee safety, digital and information safety, and workplace safety. Safety training includes the training complied with by the law and what the organizations offer.

Sales Training:

Employee sales training should be ongoing to ensure that your sales team is up to date with the most effective methods and strategies for sales. Training should cover customer service, sales techniques, managing customer relationships, up selling and cross-selling, and sales goals. Employees need to understand that sales are a process that requires ongoing training and practice to succeed.

Culture Training:

Employee culture training is designed to help employees better understand the organization's culture and values. It often includes corporate ethics, equality and diversity, communication and teamwork, customer service, and problem-solving. It can also have specific policies and procedures related to the organization's culture. In addition, employee culture training is often used to promote a positive workplace atmosphere and ensure that employees are productive and engaged.

Benefits of Employee Training and Development:

Business Impact:

As we all say health and wealth go hand in hand in the similar way training and development of an employee also impact the business of the organization, the better the skill set is, the more effective that employee would be for providing great service to the organization. You have to design your training program in such a way that it meets the organizations' overall goal because the right set of employees will be your most reliable asset. If the employee receives the right training, then he can develop future leadership skills and can be more goal-oriented. It's as simple as "If you invest in your employee their growth will invest in you."

Analyze Skill:

Every employee in your organization will be having one great skill in which the organization can train him and make him the best working employee in that field. Opposite to this, there will be some employees in your organization lacking certain sorts of skills so you can analyze it and train that employee well and provide him the opportunities to grow. This process will ensure that every employee gets proper training and can be efficient to perform various tasks.

Analyzing Skills can be Categorized and Impactful through These 3 Following Methods:

Increasing Productivity:

The employee who's been provided proper training will for sure increase his productivity level and will be more aware of the opportunities to grow in the company. In addition to this, the confidence level of the employee will also be rising which would lead to an employee being more productive.

Motivation:

The word "Motivation" plays an important role in an organization but as we all know Motivating every single day would be quite difficult and there will be days often where employees could be feeling low so here's what you can do: You can tell them about a purpose to achieve which will keep your employees motivated in a proper manner.

Decision-Making Skills:

Every employee may perform different activities but decision-making skills are one common skill every employee needs. You can first evaluate the situation, look for the possible number of solutions

(options), look around the pros and cons of the options you have, and then choose the appropriate option. An employee who has good decision-making skills will definitely help the organization to progress.

Time & Cost Saving:

This is one of the key points of Employee Training and Development, as training an employee requires a good amount of time and planning but it's all worth the efforts because the time you invest in training will result in a great performance of the individual and as far as the cost is concerned there are some effective ways through which you can lower the cost which is: Choosing online learning platforms as it's very cost-effective and is convenient, Involving everyone in the organization so that the seniors and juniors can interact with each other and exchange knowledge, etc.

Positive Employee Retention:

Most organizations spend resources and time in hiring well-qualified talents however, that effort stops once the talent is hired. This is the reason employees often leave organizations, as there is a lack of growth in their roles. Therefore, training and developing talent will help them grow and be engaged with the organization. As we know, engaged employees are less likely to jump ship and will want to stay in the organization.

Trains Future Leaders:

Training and developing the skills of your employees doesn't just benefit them but it also benefits the organization in the long term. It helps your employee be prepared for better roles and will provide them with the skill set to handle more difficult situations. It helps develop promotional skills that benefit them and will save the company recruiting expenses in the future. Furthermore, the employee at the leadership level will understand the grassroots of the organization.

Increases Workplace Engagement:

Stunted growth in the workplace can create negative habits and boredom. Training and developing employee skills will help employees feel more involved with the organization. Furthermore, it pushes employees to build a better skill set and guides them towards a better path. It also influences the company culture to change from being static to being in motion.

Helps Improve Weak Links:

Every employer recognizes a few weak links in their teams. Employees who clearly do not have the required skills. Therefore, a training program truly helps an organization understand these weaknesses and build their employee's skills. Specific training related to the employee's job will help them get better. Furthermore, helping the employee develop will help them understand their shortcomings on their own. This will push them to find resources to improve themselves.

Objectives of Training and Development:

Like all other enterprise activities, training function should also first have its objectives clearly spelled out. The objective of training and development is to alter the thinking and behavior of the employees in the direction desired by the management of the enterprise. In fact, a training programmed must be tailored to the needs of a specific company for its specific positions. If the training programmed does not accomplish the organization's needs, it may be worse than useless.

- To improve job performance by enhancing employees' knowledge and skill.
- To prepare employees well competent to discharge the new responsibilities.
- To impart skill how to operate the new machinery and equipment's.
- To reduce the wastages and accidents.
- To build a second line for more responsible positions at a later stage

This data-driven approach enables businesses to refine their strategies, predict customer needs, and proactively address potential issues, thereby building stronger, more resilient relationships. Moreover, a well-executed multi-channel customer experience can significantly impact a company's bottom line by increasing customer retention, driving up sell opportunities, and ultimately fostering loyalty. As technology continues to advance, the integration of emerging technologies like AI and machine learning into multi-channel strategies further enhances the ability to deliver hyper-personalized experiences at scale. However, implementing a successful multi-channel approach requires a deep understanding of customer journeys, a unified view of customer data, and a commitment to continuous improvement.

Statement of the Problem:

Lack of qualified instructors and consultant to undertake training courses and lack of effective communication within the organization which makes it possible for employees to know about training opportunities available to them. To identify training needs, it's crucial to develop a process to map out workers' skills. Especially in large companies, the diversity of profiles and roles complicates this process.

Objectives of the Study:

- To understand the perception of employees towards training and development activities carried out in the organization.
- To study the effectiveness of training in the organization.
- To study the factors leading to success of training of the organization.
- Explore how training and development contribute to employees' long-term career development and

succession planning within the organization.

- Evaluate how training affects employees' ability to perform their job duties effectively and efficiently.

Need of the Study:

Training is the act of increasing the knowledge and skills of an employee for doing a particular job. It utilizes a systematic and organized procedure by which employee learns technical knowledge and skills. Training refers to the teaching and learning activities carried on for the primary purpose of helping members of an organization. Training is closely related with education with needs to be differentiated for these terms. It is aimed at improving the behavior and performance of a person.

Scope of the Study:

Employee attitude towards training and development in the post-recession period help to analyze the real needs and requirement for their development. This study helps the management to determine the right kind of training & development, mentoring career planning & succession planning etc.

Hypothesis of the Study:

Following are the characteristics of hypothesis

- A hypothesis must be formulated in a way that allows it to be tested through experimentation or observation. This means it should be possible to collect empirical data that will support or refute the hypothesis. Testability is crucial for the hypothesis to be a useful tool in scientific inquiry.
- A hypothesis should be specific and clear, providing a precise statement about the expected relationship between variables. Specificity helps in designing experiments that can accurately measure and analyze these relationships. It also makes the hypothesis easier to evaluate, as clear predictions are made about what will happen under certain conditions.
- A hypothesis must be falsifiable, meaning that it can be proven false if it is incorrect. This characteristic is essential for the hypothesis to be considered scientific.

Hypothesis of the Study:

Hypothesis:

A hypothesis is an assumption that is made based on some evidence. This is the initial point of any investigation that translates the research questions into prediction. It includes components like variables, population and the relation between the variables. A research hypothesis that is used to test the relationship between two or more variables.

Characteristics of Hypothesis:

Following are the characteristics of hypothesis

- The hypothesis should be clear and precise to consider it to be reliable
- If the hypothesis is a relational hypothesis then it should be stating the relationship Between variables
- The hypothesis must be specific and should have scope for conducting more tests
- The way of explanation of the hypothesis must be very simple and it should be understood that the simplicity of the hypothesis is not related to its significance.

Sources of Hypothesis:

Following are the sources of hypothesis:

- The resemblance between the phenomenon
- Observation from past studies present day experience and from the competitors
- Scientific theories

Research Design:

A sample is a subset from the total population. A sample is a subset from the total population. It refers to the techniques or the procedure to the research would adopt in selecting items for the sample (i.e) the size of the sample.

Research Methodology:

The Researcher has chosen the questionnaire methods of data collection due to limited time in hand. While the designing data-collection procedure, adequate safeguards against bias and unreliability must be ensured. Researcher has examined the collected data for completeness, comprehensibility, consistently and reliability.

- Questionnaire
- Interview
- Observation.

Analytical Tools for the Study:

Descriptive research was undertaken to the study of the problem. The study is descriptive in nature. Descriptive research is those which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual of a group. The descriptive research describes the demographic the characteristic of the respondents and is typical concern with determining frequency with something occur show the variables vary together.

Statistical Tools:

- Simple percentage method
- Correlation
- Chi – square

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

DURATION OF THE TRAINING PROGRAMS:

Training Program Duration	No. of the Respondents	Percentage
Every month	59	59
Quarterly	18	18
Half Yearly	16	16
Once in a year	7	7
Total	100	100

TRAINING PROGRAM IS WORK BETTER FOR EMPLOYEE:

Training Programs Essential for Better Work	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	97	97
No	3	3
Total	100	100

TRAINING HELPFUL IN ENHANCING PRODUCTIVITY AND PERFORMANCE:

Training Helps in Productivity and Performance	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Agree	53	53
Strongly Agree	27	27
Neutral	14	14
Disagree	4	4
Strongly Disagree	2	2
Total	100	100

METHODS OF TRAINING:

Methods of Training	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Coaching	69	69
Job Rotation	12	12
Conference	8	8
Role Playing	10	10
Others	1	1
Total	100	100

Suggestions:

- Employees should decide and determine the training programs that they need so that they can work more effectively and efficiently, employees should decide some of the training they would like to undergo.
- The HR department should conduct briefing and debriefing sessions for employees for training as to give them an idea as to why this training is been conducted and what they have to learn in the training program conducted and also after training completion they should take feedback as to how effective was the training so that the necessary improvements in training programs can be considered and implemented.
- Apart from on-job training programs the HR Department should conduct constant value addition programs such as Time management, Stress management trainings, group dynamics, grievance redressal; these will help to add value and is also essential in today’s business scenario.
- Performance of every employee undergone training should be evaluated so as to get Improved quality of training activities, improve ability of the trainers to relate inputs to output know their understanding about the training programme conducted
- Training program should evaluate the abilities, competencies and potentials of the trainees for a particular job or work skills.
- It should aim to narrow down the gap between expected level of performance and the actual level of performance

Conclusion:

When proper training and development is provided from the organization to the employees, it helps to increase the employee’s interest towards the work and also the organization, when training and development is done by the organization, it helps to recognize the present level of the employees and what changes are needed to improve their skills, attitude knowledge, experience and also it is able to recognize the negativity of the present problems in the programs which are improving the profits, goodwill. There are lot of problems which are faced by the organization because of the lack of training they can be like accidents, injuries fights, work environment, alcohol and harassment, machineries can also be a major part of failure so training on all this teams is to be given properly and the organization should understand

the problems of the employees. Training must be given in factors which are mostly affected on the employees such as on-the-job programs.

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